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Effect of bulk and surface mechanical treatments on the tribological properties of Ti-13Nb-13Zr alloy for biomedical applications

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ABSTRACT

Ti-13Nb-13Zr (TNZ) alloy has great potential in the biomedical field due to its fully biocompatible composition and lower Young modulus value compared to the standard titanium biomaterials. As for the commercially pure Ti, the hardness and mechanical strength of TNZ can be enhanced by bulk (cold-rolling) and surface (shot-peening) mechanical treatments. However, it is still unknown how these processes, especially their combination, affect TNZ tribological properties in the simulated body fluids. This work responds to this aspect by investigating the tribological performance of TNZ in the microcrystalline, cold-rolled, shot-peened, and cold-rolled + shot-peened states. The wear behavior of the samples was tested by the pin-on-plate method (with a pin made of Al₂O₃) in the Hanks' solution at 37°C. Tribological tests were supplemented with surface characterization using microscopy and profilometry techniques, microhardness tests and electrochemical corrosion analysis. The combination of the strengthening processes: cold rolling + shot peening resulted in the highest hardness (approx. 330 HV0.2 – almost 100 units more than for the initial state) and the lowest abrasive wear with an average volume loss of 2.881 mm³, while for the unstrengthened alloy, it amounted to 3.521 mm³. Corrosion tests revealed a correlation between surface treatment (shot peening, which significantly developed topography) and corrosion resistance, as for the grinded samples, passive current density was approx. 2.5–4 times lower than for the shot-peened alloy – for both: initial and cold-rolled states. Nevertheless, for all samples good corrosion properties in Hanks' solution were received. The presented investigation revealed that the combination of cold rolling and shot-peening is the most promising in terms of TNZ tribo-corrosion performance. Moreover, this study shed light on TNZ degradation mechanisms, which are relevant during the wear process in Hank's solution.

1. Introduction

Depending on the type, implants have to meet specific requirements to ensure the success of the implantation process and the patient's safety. Biomaterials for bone implants must perform in the long term and withstand various mechanical and chemical conditions in the environment of the human body [1–4]. Ti-6Al-4V titanium alloy, due to its beneficial mechanical properties and corrosion resistance, is commonly used in implantology. Nevertheless, this material also has several drawbacks such as not fully biocompatible chemistry, precisely the presence of Al and V, which are considered as potentially harmful. Moreover, Young's modulus of Ti-6Al-4V (110 GPa) substantially exceeds the elastic modulus of the human bone (10–30 GPa) [5–7]. The misfit between Young's modulus of the biomaterial and bone can lead to bone atrophy, loosening of the implant, and bone fracture [7–10].

Material with lower Young's modulus (60–80 GPa) and great potential for application in implantology is near β-Ti alloy Ti-13Nb-13Zr (TNZ) [11–13]. It is characterized by high corrosion resistance in the environment of the human body [14–16], and contains only biocompatible chemical elements such as niobium and zirconium. Among different titanium alloys, TNZ is beneficial compared to α+β alloys due to its superior corrosion resistance [17,18] and lower Young's modulus, which, as mentioned, prevents the stress-shielding effect [19]. In comparison with other β-Ti alloys, its benefits include good mechanical properties, low density, non-toxicity, and biocompatibility [18].

One of the greatest challenges for titanium implants is obtaining suitable tribological properties. It is crucial, as wear damage is among the main causes of degradation of hard tissue replacements [20–23]. Wear processes, occurring on the implant-bone interface or the contact area of the implant components, can cause implant failure [23–25].

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Wear debris, when released to the surrounding tissue, can result in inflammatory reactions, consequently leading to bone resorption and even to implant loosening [23,24,26]. Therefore, the improvement of the tribological properties enables the extension of the longevity of implants and, consequently, the limitation of repeating surgical operations [21, 24,25,27]. Enhancement of wear resistance can be achieved by either the coatings' deposition or microstructural modifications leading to changes in the material's properties [24]. The application of hard, ceramic coatings or layers can effectively improve tribological and corrosion properties, but (depending on the method) often requires a high-temperature process [20,28–35], which can lead to unfavorable microstructural changes. Moreover, providing good adhesion to the substrate is crucial, which in various cases also requires additional surface pre-treatments [28,30,36]. The second method involves titanium hardening by large deformation processes, which introduce dislocation and grain boundary strengthening. Hardening can be achieved in the whole volume of material through e.g. cold rolling process [37–39] or only in the subsurface zone as in the case of the shot peening process [40–42]. Both methods are low-cost, do not require sophisticated equipment, and can be easily incorporated into the production process while enabling significant improvements in the mechanical properties. Moreover, the studies on titanium and its alloys subjected to the strengthening processes indicate enhancement of the tribological properties compared to the initial state [43–49]. The surface reinforcement process as shot peening results in the work-hardened layer, which can improve tribological properties, however only in the sub-surface zone, and may finally wear out during friction. As large plastic deformation processes improve mechanical properties throughout the volume of material, even after wearing the sub-surface layer, wear may be limited due to the bulk strengthening of the material. Therefore, the combination of both: bulk and surface strengthening indicates great potential for the improvement of the wear resistance.

Appearing in the literature studies on the tribological properties of the β -Ti alloys include the investigation of different new alloys and the changes in the content of alloying elements [50–56]. For Ti-13Nb-13Zr works related to its wear behavior have been focused mostly on analyzing the effect of heat treatments as well as different conditions of conducted tests (such as the presence and type of lubricant, or applied load) [23,57–62]. Little attention has been paid to verifying how alloy hardening by its plastic deformation can affect wear resistance. Single works related to this issue, consider only the effect of bulk deformation treatments [63,64]. There is a lack of studies, which show how large deformation in the sub-surface layer affects Ti-13Nb-13Zr wear resistance in the physiological fluids. Gaining knowledge about possible tribocorrosion-induced damages that can occur *in vivo* for multicomponent implants, is essential to verify and compare the application potential of modifying TNZ alloy with bulk and surface mechanical treatments.

Thereby, the aim of this study was to describe the tribological characteristic of Ti-13Nb-13Zr (TNZ) subjected to bulk or surface, as well as to the combination of bulk and surface hardening processes by large plastic deformation methods. In order to understand observed behavior, tribology investigation was extended by microscopic and topography characterization, as well as by electrochemical corrosion studies.

Table 1
Chemical composition of the Ti-13Nb-13Zr (TNZ) alloy.

Chemical element	Fe	C	N	H	O	Nb	Zr	Ti
Standard requirements [wt%]	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.08	≤ 0.05	≤ 0.012	≤ 0.15	12.5–14	12.5–14	Balance
Content [wt%]	0.032	0.007	0.008	0.002	0.062	13.6	13.03	Balance

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples preparation

The studied material was titanium alloy with niobium and zirconium: Ti-13Nb-13Zr (TNZ alloy) in the form of a rod with a diameter of 12 mm. The alloy was provided by the BIMO TECH company and meets requirements according to the ASTM F1713 standard. The chemical composition from the manufacturer certificate is presented in Table 1. In order to improve TNZ's ability to deformation, solution treatment was carried out by annealing at 800°C for 1 h and rapid cooling in water. This material was treated as an initial state in the conducted research. For tribological tests samples with a thickness of 1 mm were cut from the annealed rod. A bulk large deformation process (cold-rolling) was conducted on the sample in the form of a rod with a 10 mm diameter. Cold rolling was carried out in multiple stages to achieve a 90 % reduction in the rod thickness. Samples with approx. 8 mm of width were cut from the cold-rolled plate. The material in the initial state, as well as cold-rolled, was grinded on the SiC #600 abrasive paper. Then, part of the samples from both states were shot-peened using a Mikroblast DUO/UNO sandblasting machine in order to strengthen the sub-surface zone. The applied shots were SiO₂ spheres with a size in the range of 90–150 μ m, the conducted pressure was 0.6 MPa, and the distance between the sample and the nozzle was approximately 10 mm. To homogenize surfaces after shot peening and eliminate unfavorable surface peeling, samples were chemically etched in the diluted Kroll solution with the following composition: 1 ml 40 % HF + 2 ml 66 % HNO₃ + 500 ml distilled water. Between the particular stages of surface preparations, samples were ultrasonically cleaned in ethanol and distilled water. The designation of samples is presented in Table 2 and the process of their preparation in Fig. 1. Surface modifications and their conditions were selected based on preliminary tests and previous studies [40,41].

2.2. Material characterization

Preparation of the samples for the microstructural characterization included grinding using SiC abrasive paper with gradations: #600, #1200, #2500, polishing using a colloidal silica suspension, and etching in the Kroll reagent. The microstructure observations were carried out with a Zeiss Axio Scope A1 light microscope. The cross-sections of the shot-peened samples were observed with a Hitachi SU8000 scanning electron microscope with the PDBSE detector. The phase composition of the annealed and cold-rolled samples was analyzed using a Rigaku MiniFlex II diffractometer. The surface topography of the samples before and after tribological tests were performed with a Hitachi SU8000 scanning electron microscope with the secondary electron (SE) beam

Table 2
Samples designations.

Sample designation	State	Surface modifications
TNZ-G	initial - annealed	i) grinding (#600)
TNZ-SP	initial - annealed	i) grinding (#600) ii) shot peening (90–150 μ m, 0.6 MPa) iii) etching (Kroll solution, 5 min)
TNZ-CR-G	cold-rolled	i) grinding (#600)
TNZ-CR-SP	cold-rolled	i) grinding (#600) ii) shot peening (90–150 μ m, 0.6 MPa) iii) etching (Kroll solution, 5 min)

Fig. 1. Process of the sample preparation.

and a Wyko NT9300 optical profilometer. Surface roughness was characterized by the R_a parameter, which defines arithmetical mean height, and analyzed using Gwyddion software. The microhardness characteristic was conducted using a Falcon 500 hardness tester in the Vickers' scale of HV0.2 with at least 10 measurements for each sample. Nanoindentation tests were conducted on the TNZ alloy cross-sections using HYSITRON Triboscope 950 with a Berkovich indenter. The procedure included: (1) loading at a constant rate, (2) holding the maximum load for 2 seconds, and (3) unloading at the same rate. At least 10 indents were made on each sample with a 3 mN load, taking 10 seconds each for loading and unloading. Hardness values were calculated using the Oliver and Pharr model [65]. Nanoindentation tests of TNZ subjected to surface strengthening were performed 10 μm from the shot-peened edge.

2.3. Tribological tests

The tribological properties of TNZ alloy's analyzed states were characterized based on the reciprocating pin-on-plate tribological tests conducted on the T-17 Tribotester - method described by [66,67] with the tribological test guidelines resulting from the ASTM G99 standard. The material of the pin was an Al_2O_3 ceramic roller with a diameter of 3 mm. To simulate the conditions, that occur during the exploitation of the bone implant, wear tests were performed in the environment of the Hanks' solution at 37°C. Hanks' medium is widely used in the tribological study of biomaterials as simulated body fluid [31,34,59,62,68,69]. The solution was prepared by dissolving the following components in 1 L of the deionized water: 8.00 g of NaCl, 0.40 g of KCl, 0.06 g of $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.06 g of KH_2PO_4 , 0.20 g of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.35 g of NaHCO_3 , and 0.14 g of CaCl_2 . The final pH of the solution was 7.4 [70]. A continuous flow of a solution was ensured during the tribological test. The applied normal load was 10 N, equivalently to the nominal contact pressure of 1.4 MPa. The stroke was 2.5 mm (equaled to 10 mm of travel per cycle), the frequency of the reciprocating movement was 1 Hz, and the number of cycles was 36000, corresponding to a duration of the test of 36000 s and the total friction distance of 360 m. Wear tests were conducted for three samples from each of the analyzed states. Tribological properties were characterized by wear curves (pin holder displacement over time or distance of the wear) and Friction Force (also recorded during friction). Wear rate was calculated as a linear fit of the wear over time for two specific time ranges: 3600–14400 s and 21600–32400 s. Time ranges were selected after tests, as they corresponded to the quasi-linear wear behavior of the samples. The friction test results were supplemented with surface analysis with a Hitachi SU8000 scanning electron microscope and optical profilometer (Wyko NT9300).

2.4. Corrosion resistance

Corrosion tests were conducted to analyze chemical reactions between TNZ samples and Hanks' solution and to investigate their potential influence on tribological properties. They were carried out with a Metrohm Autolab 302 N potentiostat/galvanostat with a three-electrode system which contained a saturated Ag/AgCl reference electrode, platinum counter electrode, and the analyzed sample as the working electrode, immersed in the Hanks' solution at the temperature of 37°C. After immersion of TNZ samples in the tested solution, Open Circuit Potential (OCP) was controlled for 3600 s. Then, potentiodynamic polarization tests were started. Polarization was conducted from -0.2 V vs. OCP up to 3 V vs. Ag/AgCl with a scan rate of 1 mV/s. Tendency to corrosion in Hanks' solution was analyzed based on the current density values registered in the passive range at 0.5 V vs. Ag/AgCl ($i_{\text{pass}0.5\text{V}}$) and 1 V vs. Ag/AgCl ($i_{\text{pass}1\text{V}}$).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the samples

The XRD patterns and the microstructure of the investigated materials: TNZ in the initial state and cold-rolled are presented in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively. The individual peaks have been indexed based on the literature data [11,71–73]. The identified phases are titanium α and β . As α and martensite α' phases have the same hcp structure, the

Fig. 2. XRD patterns for TNZ alloy - initial state (TNZ) and cold rolled (TNZ-CR).

Fig. 3. Microstructure of the TNZ alloy: a) initial state, b) cold-rolled.

positions of the peaks are too similar to be distinguished [11,71]. Knowing, that TNZ alloy was annealed and quenched, it can be indicated that occurred phase is the martensite α' . Clear α/α' peaks were obtained for both states, higher for the initial state of TNZ alloy. The broadening of the peaks, observed for the cold-rolled sample (TNZ-CR), indicates significant grain refinement in the large plastic deformation process [13]. Peaks of the β phase were identified in the widening of the peaks of α/α' phase for the TNZ-CR sample. The difficulties in distinguishing the β phase for the initial state may be the reason for the very low content of this phase in the alloy or indicate its absence [11]. Conducted annealing in the temperature above the β -phase transition, followed by water quenching, may cause the full transformation of β phase into the martensitic α' phase [74–76]. The detectable by XRD analysis, concentration of the β phase for the TNZ-CR sample may, in turn, derive from the reverse phase transformation of the metastable martensite α' phase during large plastic deformation [12,13]. The XRD patterns of the shot peened samples – both: TNZ-SP and TNZ-CR-SP were analogous to the cold-rolled state TNZ-CR and did not indicate significant changes in the phase composition (Fig. TS1 in supplementary).

The microstructure analysis (Fig. 3) confirmed the presence of the martensite α' phase and revealed the residues of the primary β phase. In the initial state, the α' phase occurs in the acicular form – its fine laths are arranged inside the prior equiaxed, coarse β grains (Fig. 3a). During cold rolling, the prior grains elongation in the rolling direction occurred as the effect of large plastic deformation (Fig. 3b). The cross-section of the shot-peened samples (Fig. 4) revealed microstructural changes in the sub-surface zone. As for the cold-rolled samples significant grain and martensite α' laths refinement occurred, on the cross-section, only very fine microstructure can be observed, without distinguishing between the individual laths. However, differences in the contrast revealed the

subsurface zone strengthened by shot peening (Fig. 4b). In the initial state, the differences are more visible, as martensite laths end in the transition area of the strengthened zone of the refinement structure.

3.2. Surface topography

The SEM observations and optical profilometer tests were conducted to characterize the analyzed samples' topography. Microscopic images are presented in Fig. 5. Typical grinding morphological features were eliminated by shot peening followed by chemical etching. This procedure allowed to create the surface topography composed of craters, valleys, and peaks characteristic of peening. Conducted chemical etching allowed to eliminate the unfavorable inhomogeneity and peeling off the surface caused by shot peening, as was presented in the previous studies [40,41]. Surfaces subjected to shot peening and acid etching are homogenous and no cracks or surface damages, which can be induced by surface mechanical treatment, were noticed in SEM micrographs.

The roughness parameter R_a obtained from the analysis by optical profilometer for two different areas (313×235 and 127×95 μm) is presented in Fig. 6, and topography profiles of the characterized samples are provided in Fig. 7. As was previously noticed in SEM images, the shot peening significantly developed surfaces topography and increased roughness for both states. Whereas the R_a parameter of the initial state's surface is higher for the grinded sample than the cold-rolled one, the difference between shot-peened samples is negligible. Considering grinded samples, lower roughness for the cold rolled TNZ can be associated with its greater hardness and thereby lower susceptibility to wear during the grinding process. Similar roughness for shot-peened samples indicates that pressure applied during mechanical treatment was sufficient to create the same topography in TNZ subjected to bulk plastic

Fig. 4. Cross-section of the shot-peened samples: a) initial state, b) cold-rolled.

Fig. 5. SEM images of the surface of TNZ samples: a,b) TNZ-G; c,d) TNZ-SP; e,f) TNZ-CR-G; g,h) TNZ-CR-SP.

Fig. 6. Diagram of the R_a parameter (arithmetical mean roughness) for analyzed samples' surfaces.

deformation as in TNZ in the annealed state.

3.3. Microhardness

Results of the microhardness test in the HV0.2 Vickers scale and elastic modulus from the nanoindentation method are presented in Fig. 8. It can be noticed that shot-peening allowed for a greater increase of TNZ hardness compared to the bulk deformation with a cold-rolling technique. Although shot-peening enables more significant

strengthening, it should be kept in mind that this beneficial feature refers only to the sub-surface zone, while rolling results in the reinforcement of the entire material. Increasing hardness in the whole volume of material can be important e.g. in the case of some of the orthopedic or dental implants transferring high loads [77]. Results of hardness tests revealed that advantageous effect of bulk and surface treatment is synergistic as the highest hardness was obtained for the cold-rolled and shot-peened material. After this combined treatment hardness of TNZ (around 330 HV0.2) achieved the same value as was reported for the

Fig. 7. Topography profiles of: a) TNZ-G, b) TNZ-SP, c) TNZ-CR-G, d) TNZ-CR-SP.

Fig. 8. Results of the Vickers microhardness (HV_{0.2}) – surface measure (a) and elastic modulus - cross-section nanoindentation test (b).

Ti-6Al-4V alloy [78]. Nanoindentation tests revealed no significant differences in the elastic modulus. For all states, the value was approximately 80 GPa, and the obtained differences were close to the

measurement error (Rys.8b).

3.4. Corrosion resistance

The first step before analyzing tribological properties in Hanks fluid was verification of possible surface interaction with the solution. This allowed checking whether a possible difference in sample corrosion resistance, induced by plastic deformation, can influence tribological performance. Corrosion response was evaluated based on the results of potentiodynamic polarization tests, presented in Fig. 9. It can be noticed that corrosion potential (E_{corr}) for all of the samples was in the range from approx. -300 mV up to -100 mV vs. Ag/AgCl (Fig. 9). The largest potential value was detected for cold-rolled sample subjected to grinding, which indicates the highest suppression of anodic reactions (metal oxidation) for this material. All of the samples were in passive state in the range of applied potentials (up to $+3$ V vs. Ag/AgCl). No rapid growth of the corrosion current, which could indicate a breakdown of the oxide film, was observed during polarization tests. This is in agreement with other tests conducted in Ringer's fluid, which revealed that passive layer formed on TNZ alloy is stable up to $+8$ V vs. SCE [79, 80]. For all tested samples, the passivity ramp was achieved when the potential value reached approx. 0.3 V vs. Ag/AgCl. Once this value was exceeded, a slight but constant growth of current density with the increasing potential value was clearly visible especially for grinded samples (Fig. 9). For this reason, the current density in the passive region was designated for two selected potentials 0.5 V and 1 V vs. Ag/AgCl. Observed variation in current density during progressing polarization can be related to the insufficient growth of the oxide film throughout the experiment that cannot compensate increasing potential [81–83]. Similar characteristic of polarization curve was found for the hot-rolled Ti-13Nb-13Zr tested in Ringer's solution [84]. Additionally, for shot-peened TNZ, current peaks can be distinguished at potentials from approx. 1.75 V to 2.25 V vs. Ag/AgCl (Fig. 9). Peaks in this potential range can be associated to oxygen evolution [85] or to the phase change of TiO_2 oxide, which should occur at 2.0 – 2.2 V vs. SCE [84]. Considering the numerical values of the passive current density, it can be noticed that $i_{\text{pass}0.5\text{V}}$ was from approx. 2.5 – 4 times lower for the grinded samples compared to the shot-peened ones (Fig. 9). This indicates the better stability of the oxide films formed on their surfaces and consequently better corrosion properties. Greater passive current density detected for shot-peened material can be related to a high level of stresses in the subsurface zone and to more developed surface topography compared to the grinded materials as smoothing of TNZ was found to enhance its corrosion resistance [86]. As can be noticed, for both grinded and shot-peened samples there was virtually no effect of cold-rolling and thereby of the substrate microstructure on the values of

Fig. 9. Potentiodynamic polarization curves of the tested samples.

corrosion parameters (Fig. 9). Literature data presents contradictory conclusions related to the changes in the corrosion resistance induced by the large plastic deformation processes of TNZ [64,87,88]. Our study confirms that microstructural changes induced by conventional plastic deformation, precisely elongation grains with remaining their micro-scale dimensions, does not affect corrosion properties of TNZ alloy. This finding is in agreement with surface topography analysis for shot-peened samples, which did not reveal significant differences in the R_a values designated for TNZ in the initial and cold-rolled states. Moreover, electrochemical results demonstrate that slight discrepancies in surface roughness found for grinded samples are not important in terms of corrosion response.

3.5. Tribological properties

Results obtained from the friction tests are presented as linear wear curves and Friction Force (FF) plots. The recorded displacement value is related to the vertical movement of the Al_2O_3 pin holder during the run. This displacement includes linear wear of titanium plate (mostly), wear of the ceramic pin, as well as release and build-up of wear, sedimentation, and potentially corrosion products. The reciprocating motion used in this wear test results in Friction Force (FF) taking alternating values depending on the actual orientation of the stroke. Positive values are correlated with the force generated during the first movement (and all subsequent movements in the same orientation).

Data collected for TNZ-G samples is presented in Fig. 10. The initial break-in stage of the wear of all three samples finished after approx. 1200 seconds. In all cases, break-in resulted in negative displacement, as the first part of the wear products was released into the contact zone. The motion range (± 2.5 mm) of the whole experiment was designed so that the release of wear products was intentionally limited. Only slight differences in the amount of product release and time needed to establish regular friction conditions were observed, which can be correlated with the initial topography of the titanium samples. Break-in processes were also accompanied by high and unsettled FF values.

After the break-in, the wear process became more regular, with an almost constant wear rate ranging from 12.6 to 15.4 $\mu\text{m}/\text{h}$ for the time span starting at 3600th s and ending at 14400th s of the run. After that, the wear rate began to gradually increase, which resulted in doubling the wear rate for the time range from 21600 s up to 32400 s. This also resulted in higher FF values with quasiperiodic changes during the rest of the run.

The second stage of the wear process indicates that halfway through the experiment, new mechanisms began to appear. A higher wear rate suggests an increase in the amount and probably a change in the form of wear products. The periodicity of changes in the friction force values also indicates the occurrence of different wear mechanisms.

SEM observations of the samples after the wear test (Fig. 11), revealed that the Al_2O_3 pin was covered with numerous and different size TNZ chips with noticeable parallel scratches visible on their surface. EDS analysis (Fig. TS2 in supplementary) confirmed, that chips are made of TNZ alloy – Ti-13Nb-13Zr, with almost no oxygen detected and no significant amount of solution components observed (Na: <1 % weight, Cl: <1 % weight). Based on this observation, the wear process, at least in its final stage, was composed of both TNZ – Al_2O_3 and TNZ – TNZ chip interactions.

EDS analysis of the scar on all TNZ samples, both cleaned and not cleaned, revealed no change in alloy composition, no detectable surface oxidation, and no solution sedimentation, but small numerous points of aluminum concentration. The wear mechanism certainly involved the crumbling of Al_2O_3 grains, however further weight analysis suggests that the process was not very intense.

Observations of the uncleaned sample after the test (Fig. 11c), showed a large amount of wear products, mostly concentrated in deep and wide scratches along the whole surface of the scar on the TNZ-G sample. More in-depth SEM analysis (Fig. 12a) revealed that observed

Fig. 10. Linear wear curves and Friction Force plots of TNZ-G samples.

Fig. 11. Samples after wear test (TNZ-G – test 1): a) Al_2O_3 pin b) TNZ-G plate (cleaned), c) TNZ-G plate (not cleaned)[areas marked as A, B and C were selected for more detailed analysis on Fig. 12].

Fig. 12. TNZ-G plate after wear test 1: a) area A presenting small, semi-round wear products located mostly inside large scratches, b) area B presenting chip detachment area from the semi-flat surface, c) area C presenting chip detachment area from the edge of the large scratch.

earlier wear products took the form of numerous semi-round granules of size from 1 to 10 μm in diameter. The morphology and size of these wear products resembled the effects of the milling process [89–91], including tests with very similar alloys [92]. Repetitive motion with frequent change in the direction and limited release of wear products caused the cold welding and fracturing known from the milling process, especially

since in both cases, tested material works against much harder material. Moreover, the shape, bimodal size distribution and observed internal porosity correspond to the results obtained for similar working times [92].

Further analysis performed on the cleaned surface (Fig. 12b,c) also revealed areas, from where large (>100 μm) chips of TNZ were torn off

and attached to the Al_2O_3 pin surface. Titanium alloy chips were torn off from the edges of large furrows (Fig. 12c) but also directly from the semi-flat surface of the titanium alloy (Fig. 12b).

The wear process of TNZ-SP samples proceeded in two different ways (Fig. 13). First type was very similar to the one observed for TNZ-G samples: short break-in process, linear stage with constant Friction Force, and finally, intensified wear with increasing FF values. Those samples presented very similar wear rates and final wear at the end of the run.

After the test, the surface of the ceramic pins and titanium alloy resembled the ones observed for TNZ-G samples. On the other hand, some samples of this type presented exceptionally good wear behavior, including reduced wear rates and final wear (Fig. 13 – test 3). Those samples also presented lower FF values and extended linear stage of the process (up to 20000 s). The second stage (the one with intensified wear rate) started with a short drop in displacement value and further proceeded with observed earlier characteristics, but much smaller intensity.

All this caused scars on TNZ plates to be much shallower (Fig. 14), however, bottoms of these samples were very similar to the ones, on which a more abrupt process occurred. They were covered with wide scratches, filled with round globular wear products, but slightly smaller in size. Also, the surface of the Al_2O_3 pins resembled the ones described earlier, but chips of TNZ alloy attached to their surface were noticeably smaller and thinner.

Larger chips were not only distributed on ceramic pin surfaces but also could be found stuck inside deep scratches, mostly near their ends (Fig. 15a). The other areas, where they can be found, were among the wear products deposited on the surface around the scars. In all cases, those deposits contained both types of wear products - round small lumps and large chips, and absolutely no other type or size of wear products. The observed only two types of wear products bring to mind two main stages of the wear process, where one of them is less intensive and more stable and the other one is more abrupt and inconstant, mostly due to large chip detachment (Fig. 15b) and involving adhesive wear (Fig. 15c) [90,93].

Samples after cold rolling and grinding (TNZ-CR-G) presented the spread of tribological properties, even though all samples were taken from the same flat bar. Mostly due to the relatively high overall wear rate at the first stage (3600–14400 s), they also showed the most linear wear curves – the smallest differences between two arbitrarily selected

stages of the run (Fig. 16). Samples subjected to strain hardening had also most inconsistent Friction Force values. The scars on those samples looked very same as the ones created on TNZ-G samples (Fig. 17). One visible difference was that many of the wide scratches were covered by a deformed material, creating deep and partially closed cavities (Fig. 18b, c). Creation and closing of furrows edges over scratch would be rather expected on a less hardened material, than the one after cold rolling.

A similar behavior was observed for another strengthened material – TNZ after cold rolling but additionally subjected to a surface hardening by a shot peening (TNZ-CR-SP). These samples presented a range of wear properties (Fig. 19). Two of the runs had a standard form with the spread already observed for TNZ-CR-G samples. The third sample (Fig. 19 - test 2) presented, also observed earlier, exceptionally good wear behavior. First, the linear stage of the run was exceptionally long with the smallest wear rate and FF values observed. The second stage started with a visible drop in displacement and was followed by rather intensive wear ($19.7 \mu\text{m}/\text{h}$), considering data collected for another good performing material – TNZ-SP sample ($15.4 \mu\text{m}/\text{h}$).

The scar on this special/unique sample was shallow with rather smooth scratches visible on its bottom (Fig. 20). The Al_2O_3 pin after the test resembled any other pin used in this experiment. It was covered with numerous TNZ chips. The position of the largest ones corresponded with the position of the widest and deepest scratches on the TNZ surface. Most of the large chips were covered with parallel scratches. The main wear products of this test were numerous, small, and almost spherical grains. After the test, they were mostly found inside wide scratches (Fig. 21a) and of course, in wear products deposits around the scar. Only a few large flat chips were found on this sample. Even flake-type wear residues, visible on the end of the scar (Fig. 20c) were actually agglomerates of the small grainy products.

Observations performed with higher magnification showed that scratch edges are actually jagged, resembling the effects of the micro-cutting process with the presence of typical chips on the surface (Fig. 21b). There were much less large craters created when large flakes were torn from the surface. If found, they were rather shallow and smaller in size.

All scars were subjected to Optical Profilometry analysis. The main reason was to establish the depth of the scars and the volume of removed material. Height maps also revealed rather equal wear along the entire length of the scars (Fig. 22), It also showed, that some of the material

Fig. 13. Linear wear curves and Friction Force plots of TNZ-SP samples.

Fig. 14. Samples after wear test (TNZ-SP – test 3): a) Al₂O₃ pin b) TNZ-SP plate (cleaned), c) TNZ-SP plate (not cleaned) [areas marked as D, E and F were selected for more detailed analysis on Fig. 15].

Fig. 15. TNZ-SP plate after wear test 3: a) area D presenting TNZ chip stuck inside large scratch and semi-round wear products located on the bottom of the scratch, b) area E presenting chip detachment area from the semi-flat surface, c) area F presenting traces of adhesive wear on semi-flat surface of TNZ sample.

Fig. 16. Linear wear curves and Friction Force plots of TNZ-CR-G samples.

was piled up on the sides and ends of the scars, due to plastic deformation. No particular differences in size, form, or amount of these bulges were found. It also showed that scars on samples of TNZ, that presented good wear behavior (both after shot peening: TNZ-SP and TNZ-CR-SP), did not differ much in terms of topography or general appearance (despite the depth). Cross-sections of the scars were

compared (Fig. 23) and in all cases, their depth correlated with final displacement of tribological tests. In some cases, scar cross-section analysis presented uneven wear in a direction perpendicular to the movement of the pin (Fig. 23). Slight slope on the bottom of the scars (Fig. 23b – test 3 or Fig. 23d – test 1, all exaggerated due to the axis scale used) is rather related to material properties (not entirely uniform on the

Fig. 17. Samples after wear test (TNZ-CR-G – test 3): a) Al₂O₃ pin b) TNZ-CR-G plate (cleaned), c) TNZ-CR-G plate (not cleaned) [areas marked as G, H and I were selected for more detailed analysis on Fig. 18].

Fig. 18. TNZ-CR-G plate after wear test 3: a) area G presenting TNZ deformed edge of the large scratch and semi-round wear products located on the bottom of the scratch, b) area H presenting chip detachment area from the semi-flat surface, c) area I presenting traces of adhesive wear and deformed and flattened edge of the large scratch.

Fig. 19. Linear wear curves and Friction Force plots of TNZ-CR-SP samples.

flat bar after rolling) than a contact zone geometry, as the Al₂O₃ pins and TNZ alloy plates were properly measured and leveled before the tests.

Quantitative analysis of the scars is presented in Table 3. The depth of the scars was established for a 2 by 2 mm square area of the center of the scars. The same area was also used to determine the roughness

parameter of the scar bottoms (to establish this value, the bottoms of the scars were first leveled, so the observed in some cases slope, would not affect the presented parameter).

The roughness parameter of the scars' bottoms was very similar for samples with no hardening or one type of hardening applied only ($R_a =$

Fig. 20. Samples after wear test (TNZ-CR-SP – test 2): a) Al_2O_3 pin b) TNZ-CR-SP plate (cleaned), c) TNZ-CR-SP plate (not cleaned) [areas marked as J, K and L were selected for more detailed analysis on Fig. 21].

Fig. 21. TNZ-CR-SP plate after wear test 2: a) area J presenting small, semi-round wear products located both in shallow and wide scratches and on flat surfaces, b) area K presenting effects of the micro-cutting process, c) area L presenting flattened surface with shallow chip detachment area.

Fig. 22. Optical Profilometry height maps of TNZ samples after tribological tests: a) TNZ-G sample – test 1, b) TNZ-SP sample – test 3, c) TNZ-CR-G sample – test 3 d) TNZ-CR-SP sample – test 2.

~3.5 μm). It is mostly affected by large and deep scratches spread over the entire length of the scars. Due to measurement limitations and applied scan size, some topography features, like semi-closed cavities on samples after cold rolling and grinding (TNZ-CR-G), weren't appropriately registered. A smaller scan size (with better resolution), would better describe unique features, but also would strongly affect the averaged value and make it less representative. A significantly smaller roughness parameter ($R_a = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$) was found on TNZ-CR-SP samples, which corresponded well to the SEM observations of the scars.

Volume loss of TNZ material (obtained from Optical profilometry) correlated to a greater extent with the mass loss of the samples (the density of the TNZ alloy was 5.28 g/cm^3). For both measurements, the highest averaged material loss was found for samples with no bulk or surface hardening (TNZ-G samples). The better overall performance of the other groups of samples was strongly influenced by some exceptional behavior of shot-peened samples and lesser repeatability of results for cold-rolled and grinded samples (TNZ-CR-G). Without their unusual tribological performance (not always observed), averaged material loss

Fig. 23. Scar cross-sections of TNZ samples, based on Optical profilometry: a) TNZ-G sample, b) TNZ-SP sample, c) TNZ-CR-G sample, d) TNZ-CR-SP sample.

would be similar. It is also clearly visible on scars cross-sections presented in Fig. 23 and the depth of the scars presented in Table 3. Samples without any hardening process had the deepest and largest in volume scars. In terms of volume or mass loss, each type of hardening resulted in better performance and the combination of them resulted in the best properties. This also applies to the calculated average friction coefficient (Table 3).

The volume or depth of the scars did not correlate with the final wear results. In most cases, the depth of the scars obtained from Optical Profilometry was 10–30 μm higher than the overall wear registered by the tribotester device. It clearly shows that, during the test, wear products remained in the contact zone and played a significant role in wear processes. A similar amount of wear products formed during the break-in process, which resulted in a negative displacement value for most samples at this early stage of the run.

SEM analysis showed that there were only two types of wear products found on the samples after tests. The first ones were very small ($d = 1\text{--}10\ \mu\text{m}$) but very numerous round grains. They were found mostly inside deep scratches and around the scars. The second ones were rather large and flat chips of TNZ alloy. TNZ chips were found inside the largest scratches, around scars, and also attached to ceramic pins' surfaces. The wear of the Al_2O_3 was rather small (hardly observed weight loss), however, EDS analysis showed that small grains of ceramic were present on every TNZ sample after the test.

The presence of only two types of wear products indicates that two main wear mechanisms occurred during tests. The first one was composed of micro-cutting and microchips forming (Fig. 21b). Due to reciprocating motion, those chips first tended to curl. Further pin movement and limited ability to leave the contact zone, caused grinding of these microchips into semi-round globes. The second mechanism involved large chips detachment from the TNZ surface (Fig. 15b) and their adhesive attachment to the ceramic pin surface. Those chips served as a main “tool” engraving the bottom of the scar with wide and deep scratches.

Two wear mechanisms were surely associated with the distinct two-stage wear behavior of all samples. The formation of small but numerous round grains is responsible for the first semi-linear stage of the wear. This stage was also characterized by semi-constant values of friction force and significantly lower wear rates. The second stage usually started just after the halfway point of the wear process when the second, more abrupt, and rather adhesion-based process joined. The formation of large chips, the creation of deep scratches, and later chips release, significantly increased wear rate and Friction Force values. It also made FF values unstable. Changes in FF can be related to the attachment and later release of TNZ chips from ceramic surfaces. No visible changes or variations of displacement during FF increase or drop suggest that the amount of TNZ material attached to Al_2O_3 pins changed in terms of coverage, not height.

Unique properties of selected shot-peened (surface-hardened) samples can be related to the extended first stage of the wear process. Surface hardening significantly postponed the occurrence of the second wear mechanism, mostly due to the higher strength of the material,

residual compressive stress near the surface, or less amount of potential crack nucleation points (uniformity of the surface). In these cases, a moment of first chips creation was easily observed on displacement curves (Fig. 13 – test 3 and Fig. 19 - test 2) as a short drop right before the increase of the wear rate. This exceptionally good wear behavior wasn't observed on all samples of this type, probably due to the non-completely uniform strengthening during cold rolling or shot peening processes. It is also possible that the second stage or second wear mechanism requires certain threshold conditions to occur, which apparently were close to the load, speed, travel, or temperature used in this experiment.

3.6. Influence of the surface properties on the tribological behavior

As the working conditions of the bone implants include not only mechanical loads and tribological processes but also introduce the environment of the body fluid, it is crucial to examine samples comprehensively and compile the studies. Therefore, the performed research contains either: wear tests in the Hanks' solution and corrosion investigation in the same medium. Moreover, the effect of the surface modifications and strengthening processes was characterized by topography analysis with optical profilometry and microhardness test.

The obtained results indicate the influence of surface morphology on the corrosion behavior, while no strong impact of the cold-rolling process was observed. It appears that for grinded samples (in both states: initial and cold-rolled), the stability of the surface oxides was improved in comparison with the shot-peened state. Moreover, potentiodynamic polarization tests in the Hanks' solution did not reveal interruptions of the passive layer or the occurrence of the pitting corrosion, and the results exhibit good corrosion properties of all samples in the applied solution. However, during the wear test, the oxide layer is abraded and, due to the continuous friction, repassivation is hindered, therefore the character of processes occurring on the surface may change [61,94]. Nevertheless, the microscopic observation and analysis of the scars after wear tests did not reveal corrosion of the samples, and investigation of the created products indicates their origin from the tribological, not corrosion, processes. Therefore, the compared results did not demonstrate any significant influence of the corrosion on the wear processes in the Hanks' solution. While corrosion resistance slightly depended on the surface topography, no such relation for tribological properties was observed. As roughness changes were at the level of less than a micrometer, they were aligned in the first seconds of the friction. As mentioned above, only two types of wear residues were detected for all samples. Globular, small granules and larger chips, attached to the scar area and Al_2O_3 pin, varied only in size or distribution, but not shape or morphology – even for the shot-peened samples. These wear products were present for each sample and, appearing between plate and pin, were involved in every friction test. Hence, it can be concluded, that the surface topography did not significantly influence wear conditions. Therefore, it follows, that the factor with the greatest impact on the tribological character is material strengthening. The reinforcement processes, both: bulk and surface, resulted in a significant increase in the

Table 3
Wear test results based on Optical Profilometry, Tribological Tests parameters, and Weighing of the samples.

sample designations	Optical Profilometry Analysis			Tribological test analysis					Weight Analysis			
	Volume loss	Depth of scar center	R _a of leveled scar center	Wear rate for 1st* range	Wear rate for 2nd* range	Averaged FF for 1st* range	Averaged FF for 2nd* range	Averaged COF	Final wear	Al ₂ O ₃ pin mass change	TNZ plate mass change	
	[mm ³]	[mm]	[μm]	[μm/h]	[μm/h]	[N]	[N]		[μm]	[mg]	[mg]	
TNZ-G	test 1	3.580	226	3.32	13.7	26.4	3.49	9.07	0.65	167.6	-0.867	-18.977
	test 2	3.552	219	3.35	15.4	23.1	4.83	8.67	0.70	177.7	-0.950	-18.864
	test 3	3.432	208	3.67	12.6	23.0	3.99	7.98	0.60	181.0	nd**	-18.206
	Av.	3.521	218	3.44	13.9	24.2	4.1	8.6	0.65	175.4	-0.909	-18.682
TNZ-SP	test 1	3.505	211	2.99	15.1	25.5	3.95	9.20	0.67	205.5	-1.798	-19.333
	test 2	3.638	238	4.79	18.4	24.1	3.85	8.70	0.65	211.5	-0.918	-20.637
	test 3	2.322	152	2.97	8.1	15.4	2.92	5.93	0.47	118.6	-0.668	-14.254
	Av.	3.155	200	3.58	13.8	21.7	3.6	7.9	0.60	178.5	-1.128	-18.075
TNZ-CR-G	test 1	3.142	196	3.87	16.8	24.0	2.93	7.42	0.55	196.0	-0.795	-18.085
	test 2	2.966	184	2.87	15.4	21.3	3.82	8.51	0.64	171.7	-1.012	-16.913
	test 3	3.528	216	4.05	18.5	26.6	3.86	8.55	0.65	219.3	-1.158	-19.136
	Av.	3.212	199	3.59	16.9	24.0	3.5	8.2	0.61	195.7	-0.988	-18.045
TNZ-CR-SP	test 1	3.276	200	2.42	17.6	23.0	3.77	8.68	0.64	218.4	-1.068	-18.706
	test 2	2.394	142	2.94	7.8	19.7	2.38	5.66	0.41	116.5	-0.504	-14.279
	test 3	2.974	176	2.42	12.6	24.0	3.09	8.64	0.61	179.4	-1.058	-18.465
	Av.	2.881	173	2.59	12.7	22.3	3.1	7.7	0.55	171.5	-0.877	-17.150

* 1st range: 3600–14400 s; 2nd range: 21600–32400 s

** sample damaged during weighing

hardness of the, respectively: whole material and the subsurface zone. Concurrently, they improve tribological properties by limiting wear and tearing off plate material, as indicated by smaller – in size and number – observed residues. This may be due to the higher subsurface hardness, nevertheless, an obvious correlation between microhardness and wear resistance cannot be established. Most of the samples revealed two stages of wear performance. The first one was less intensive, more stable and associated with abrasive wear, which led to the formation of small semi-round particles. Their presence in the friction zone, led to a process similar to the fretting. The second stage also involved adhesive wear and further formation of large chips due to the delamination process. The presence of these two types of wear depended on the method of strengthening of the TNZ alloy: bulk, surface, or both. Furthermore, results for the strengthened materials differ for various tests of the same sample type. Differences may arise from non-uniform hardening during the reinforcement process or local lower repeatability of the shot peening. Regardless, the sample with the highest hardness – TNZ-CR-SP – also revealed the best tribological properties, which indicates the significant potential of the combined strengthening processes: cold rolling and further shot peening.

Further studies will investigate the influence of different strengthening processes on the tribo-corrosion properties of TNZ. β -titanium alloy will be subjected to large plastic deformation processes such as: accumulative roll bonding (ARB) and hydro-extrusion (HE). The studies will contain comparisons with currently applied in biomedicine Ti-6Al-4V alloy and the tribo-corrosion properties will be examined in the tribological system combined with the ongoing corrosion tests.

4. Conclusions

Conducted studies presented the investigation of the tribological properties of the Ti-13Nb-13Zr alloy against Al_2O_3 in the environment of the Hanks' solution, which simulates body fluids. Two methods of material strengthening – bulk and surface – were conducted: cold rolling and shot peening, respectively. Based on the obtained results it can be concluded that conducted shot peening improves the microhardness of TNZ to a greater extent than cold rolling with a deformation of 90 % (with the differences between the samples of more than 50 units for shot peening and approx. 40 units for cold rolling). However, this applies only to the subsurface zone. A combination of cold rolling and further surface reinforcement (TNZ-CR-SP sample) enables an even enhanced increase in subsurface hardness to about 330 HV0.2 with simultaneous improvement of the mechanical properties of the entire material. Moreover, this combination provides the best wear resistance among the tested samples with the lowest average volume loss (of 2.881 mm³) and friction coefficient of 0.55. Studies also revealed two different main wear mechanisms of Ti-13Nb-13Zr alloy during tribological processes: micro-cutting, leading to the formation of microchips and their grinding, and engraving of the scar due to the formation and attachment to the pin of the larger wear residues. Performed corrosion tests indicate good resistance of the TNZ alloy in the environment of the Hanks' solution and the lack of intensive and destructive corrosion processes, which could influenced the wear resistance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kowalczyk Agnieszka: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Pura Jaroslaw:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Sotniczuk Agata:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Garbacz Halina:** Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

We hereby declare that the authors have no other relevant affiliations or financial conflicts with the subject matters or materials discussed in the manuscript. We confirm that all authors have checked the manuscript and have agreed to the submission.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.triboint.2025.110605](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2025.110605).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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